

THE IMPACT OF BATTLE GROUND MOBILE INDIA ON ADOLESCENTS

***Dr Raino Bhatia **Dr Neelam Kumari**

**Principal, ACE, Eternal University, Himachal Pradesh*

***HOD, ACA&SS, Eternal University, Himachal Pradesh*

Abstract

We are living in 21st century where artificial intelligence and motion graphics have emerged in a new way and brought transformation in technology due to continuous progress in the field of computers. Due to which online games are gaining more and more popularity among children today. The children spend most of their time in the internet, playing online video games. Battleground Mobile India is the one which is mostly discussed among children and is viral with social media and played mostly by school and college students. This study is basically focused on identifying the reasons behind addiction among teenagers. Qualitative Research design was used for this study to understand and analyse the responses of adolescents. The sample of the study is 30. The study focuses on adolescents. Data were collected through individual interviews. The interview was conducted on an average of 20-30 minutes. The researcher collected the recurrent meaningful themes from the conversations

*The advantages of playing Battleground Mobile India are better visual attention, motor control abilities, increasing socialization, attention, multitasking and better judgement whereas limitations of the game are game addiction, aggression, emotional upheaval, distancing from family and increase in anxiety, stress and **depression**.*

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eiirj/>

Introduction

Online video games has become popular among youth; it is said to bring in changes in physical, mental, social and emotional aspects of an individual (Lo, Wang and Fang 2005) .In several instances online games seem to provide positive as well as negative consequences, as in case for relaxation, it might help them to overcome from their stressful past experiences and also for improving learning outcomes (Autio, 2018).

Recently launched Battleground Mobile India is the most widely used games in adolescents. After PUBG Mobile's ban in India back in September last Year, Krafton has finally managed to bring back in the form of Battlegrounds Mobile India on July 2,2021 which is a slightly tweaked version of PUBG Mobile exclusively to the Indian audiences. The game content might not be suitable for all ages for some adolescents it seems to be too aggressive, while it's quite normal for others.

This game is attracting children day by day and it has become more serious than the usual. Media reports that online games make people to lose their efficiency in their life. Many cases have different kind of consequences after playing it, running away from home, experiencing serious addiction, exam failures, hospitalization, drinking acid, and even death (Mamun and Griffiths 2019)

Even Gujarat government was the first to take action and banned the game of PUBG because there was a downfall in the academic performance of the students (NDTV Gadgets 360 Staff, January 2019)

The present study focuses on revealing the truth behind engaging with online games especially Battleground Mobile India even after being aware of the experiences or consequences that others would have.

About the Study

- To identify the reason and motivation of adolescents playing battleground Mobile India
- To understand the physical, psychological, emotional and social changes experienced by the players of Battleground Mobile India.

Qualitative research design (phenomenological approach) was adopted for this research; phenomenological approach (realistic phenomenology) to understand / analyse the responses of college students. The phenomenological approach enables the researcher to understand the nature and meaning of an experience for a particular group of people in a particular setting (Moustakas, 1994) by allowing the researcher to take part in their stories. This will enable the researcher to understand the subjective nature of the phenomenon being investigated (Kennedy, Terrell & Lohle, 2005) by laying aside the prevailing understandings of the phenomenon and revisit our immediate experience.

The samples in qualitative studies are much smaller than those in quantitative studies. There is a point of diminishing returns to a qualitative sample - as the study goes on, more data does not necessarily lead to more *information*. While there are other factors that affect sample size in qualitative studies, researchers generally use saturation as a guiding principle during their data collection. Creswell (2007) indicated that a sample size of about 25 or so individuals, all who share the same experience under investigation, often produces saturation in qualitative studies. This study finally had the sample size of 27 PUBG (online video game) players in the age range of 18-24 years (chosen using purposive sampling technique) who were willing to share their experiences.

A variety of open-ended questions were chosen to elicit the most information possible in the time available. Data were collected through the individual interviews individual's perspectives and experiences are being explored. Each interview on an average took 20-30 minutes. Nonverbal behaviours and the interview context were also noted and it becomes the part of the data.

The following were some of the questions (respondents were probed further to explain/describe specific events connected to the theme behind each question):

After collecting the data, the participants' narratives are analysed to acquire a feeling for their idea in order to understand them fully. The second step is to extract the significant statements a process called horizontalization. After horizontalization, for each of the significant statement meanings are formulated. The process is *repeated* across participants' stories and recurrent meaningful themes are clustered. The *researcher* integrates the resulting themes into a rich description of the phenomenon under study (textual description).

These themes are reduced to an essential structure that offers an explanation of the behaviour how it was experienced) structured description. The phenomenological research ends with the reader's understanding better the essential, invariant structure (or essence of the experience, recognizing the sample unifying meaning of the experience exists.

Student Engagement with Battle Ground Mobile India

A Phenomenological Study

1. When do you start playing Battle Ground Mobile India?
2. What motivates you to play it and what makes you to continue the play?
3. Duration (minimum and maximum hours) of playing Battle Ground Mobile India?
4. Maximum no. Of. Matches played in a day?
5. How you felt when you killed someone and killed by someone in your first match?
6. Is playing Battle Ground Mobile India similar to PUBG ?
7. Do you find any use of playing it?

8. Any personal changes observed after playing Battle Ground Mobile India?
9. What do you think about players Battle Ground Mobile India?
10. How non Battle Ground Mobile India players are seeing you?
11. How did you feel after winning Battle Ground Mobile India?
12. How would you feel after being attacked or killed during the last minute of the game?
13. Have you ever planned things in advance or finished up your work quickly or compromised or postponed your work to play Battle Ground Mobile India?
14. Have you ever felt that you cannot stay away from Battle Ground Mobile India?
15. Is there anything not so good about Battle Ground Mobile India?

Results and Discussion

The respondent's narratives were analysed to acquire a feeling of their ideas in order to understand them fully. The following are some of the themes that have come up through this study, as to why respondents continued to stay engaged with Battle Ground Mobile India .

Sense of Satisfaction/ Overcoming the Feeling of Incompleteness.

Players who play Battle Ground Mobile India felt that they experience a sense of positive satisfaction over it; games not always provide negative consequences, it sometimes could also help to overcome their feeling of incompleteness. From the interview many respondents pointed out that they have some sense of satisfaction whenever they achieved in the game and that seems to be a motivating factor. Moreover, the curiosity that rises from the trending news also motivates them to know what it is and the satisfaction that arises after playing is limitless.

Excerpts from the participants are Sense of Accomplishment given below:

"I'm an NDA Aspirant; the nature of the game is like a military operation ground: thus its motives and I resolve my desires to join, by playing it.

"Trending news in social media it increases curiosity to play and it provides satisfaction when acknowledge what is happening in Battle Ground Mobile India"

"It helps me to pass the time when I'm bored and idle, when I'm playing it: I feel that I was engaged in sometime without sitting idle"

Thus, it shows that the players get the motivation to continue playing it and as they get satisfaction which they cannot get from other activities. Moreover, most of them play Battle Ground Mobile India in order to compete with their friends and it gives them the feeling of staying connected in with the group when they know and play Battle Ground Mobile India. In a study conducted on personality traits and life satisfaction among online game players, the results indicate that there is a significant relationship between personality traits and life satisfaction, especially in openness and conscientiousness (Chen, L.S. Tu, H.H., & Wang, E.S., 2008).

Sense of Accomplishment

Playing online games always seem to provide some kind of pleasure, perceived sense of achieving something, and the feel good it provides. The thrilling experience and the challenge of playing/winning against group of people motivate players to continue in along run, for a longer duration. And also, emerging as a winner from 100 players gives players the ultimate sense of fulfilment and accomplishment. Sometimes winning a game also helps in releasing the skills that one possesses.

From the interview many respondents denote that winning a game provides happiness and pride as winning a match is not an easy task, one has to outplay 100 players in order to win a chicken dinner. Thus, winning in this game provides

enormous happiness. Excerpts from the interview are given below:

"Winning a match in Battle Ground Mobile India is comparatively difficult than other games, but gives more satisfaction within a single game" "Gives a feeling that I had achieved something great and when I won a game I used to show it to my friends"

"It provides happiness for sometimes until I move on to other work"

"It also helps in realizing the skills that we possess as winning a game involves a lot of effort" "In order to win a match, and when I kill someone, I felt like a soldier in a border and I feel proud about myself While I kill someone, it drives me to kill more to win more matches"

"When I win a match, it induces intention to play another match and it gradually increases day by day"

A research done by Jeng S. & Teng. C. On personality and motivation for playing online games, the results show the personality traits including the extraversion, openness and conscientiousness play a role in teamwork and motivation. While neuroticism is negatively correlated with motivation. Some players prefer PUBG as it provides a sense of accomplishment in a single game thus; it motivates them to continue in a long run.

Thus, playing the game, it itself a pleasure and in addition, achieving a game is a believed like a great achievement. Also, a study done by Lee, M. (2009) shows that the flow occurred in the playing online game zone is primarily important for continuing the game than other factors like perceived enjoyment.

Improvement in the Sense of self.

It is also important to note that playing online games not always provides negative consequences; it sometimes can help in improving the skills, and also helps in learning some unknown information regarding the game that can be related to the real world.

The respondents said that they came to know about the real guns its name and virtually using it through Battle Ground Mobile India, as the game is designed in the way that includes the real gun's name Also, many respondents point out that they experienced better eye hand coordination than before, and sometimes it also helped in being more vigilant and alert, improving their problem solving skills/ability.

Excerpts from the interview are given:

"It helps in connecting with more people, and applying mind to play tactfully for winning a game"

"I learn to be more alert in real life, and my reaction time seemed to have improved"

Thus, playing games might also help in improving one's skills and sense of itself. Liberman, D. A. (1997) conducted a study on Interactive video games for health promotion; it was found that the game helped players to learn about prevention, self-care and that further improved health –related skills and behaviours.

Perceived Self-Control

Everything in this world has both positives and negatives; we preferably tend to experience whatever we believe in. Online games also have both positive negative; it all depends on how an individual takes it. Usually once entered into a gaming zone, it is hard for people to discontinue; one should have control over their behaviour so that they can choose to experience positive effects.

While some of the respondents said that they have the control over playing game, few pointed that Battle Ground Mobile India is a productive one where many people use it as a tool for advertisement in order to attract many people.

Excerpts from the interview are given:

"Some players are aware about the reason why they are playing and some may not thus lead to negative consequences and they become addicted to it"

“Some players play Battle Ground Mobile India as a time pass while few may not notice or is aware of what is happening around them when they play Battle Ground Mobile India”

“Some spends their whole day by playing it; they are also willing to invest and buy electronic gadgets for just for playing Battle Ground Mobile India”

As mentioned above, it depends on how we perceive things. Many players also take Battle Ground Mobile India as more important than anything thus it results in negative consequences while some players might be conscious about why they use it as for relaxation purpose. A research on Online gaming addition shows that the role of sensation seeking, self-control, neuroticism, aggression, state anxiety and trait anxiety are clearly associated with the online game addition (Mehroof, M., &Griffiths, M., D., 2010).

Increased Negative Emotions/Affect

As the game nature is violent, it sometimes seems to affect individual’s emotions and behaviours; people were seemed to be less aggressive after playing this game. Moreover, they tend to shout at people when they distract their game.

Some respondents note that they tend to shout at people when they distract their game and sometimes they avoid contact with people and important phone calls that comes during the game.

Excerpts from the interview are given:

“Sometimes I tend to be little more aggressive than before when I play PUBG. I used to shout at people when they distract me during the match”

“I used to ignore calls even if it is important during the match”

“I experience some physical pain and have a deep sleep after playing it”

Thus, playing Battle Ground Mobile India sometimes gives pain and anger, but players tend to avoid it as they are highly focussed on playing it alone even it seems to provide negative consequences. A study was conducted on cognitive and psychological predictors of the negative outcomes associated with playing MMOGs (massively multiplayer online games). The results noted that psychological dependency and deficient self-regulation plays an important role in negative consequences associated with online gaming (Liu, M., Peng, W., 2009).

Threat to Personal Development

Some people argue that playing Battle Ground Mobile India seems to involve all players and keep them in a state where they don’t care about what happens to them. Or to people around. Sometimes it prevents people from focusing on their work even it is highly important: players of Battle Ground Mobile India ignores it in order to play it.

Excerpts from the interview given below:

“Non-players might not have enough facilities to play on their mobiles so they criticize players”

“Non-players might not know how to play Battle Ground Mobile India, so they denote Battle Ground Mobile India as time consuming and useless”

“Some might turn furious when we play it as they might not prefer this kind of games”

Some of the players of Battle Ground Mobile India tells that this game became threat for one’s development when we became completely engrossed in it. It’s important to have control over it then playing it and it seems to affect people worse than they lack the control over the game. A research on effect of video game on child development states that student who played the violent virtual reality game can have a higher heart rate: they were also reported to go through more dizziness. And exhibited more aggressive thoughts then those who played non- violent game.

Dependency

As mentioned before everything has its own positives and negatives in order to avoid negative people should have control over the game. Having self-control helps players to overcome from their negative experiences.

Some players denote that they have control over the game while other some doesn't it makes to look at the game alone by ignoring other works around them. When it comes to topic of banning Battle Ground Mobile India some doesn't mind it even it's banned while some players say that it is difficult for them to overcome from game.

Excerpts from the interview given below.

“we should know how to use and prevent our self from addiction other should not argue to ban it by focusing on one side perspective”

“everything contains boon and bane. The effects depends on how we take it”

“I feel less difficult to overcome it. But banning also suggested when It effects person's life worse”

“I feel very bad if Battle Ground Mobile India was banned the happiness its provide can -not be replaced by others”

When its coming to banning its important to focus on both sides the positives and the negatives as it also used for and relaxation and it also helps some people to from their past negative experiences. On the side. It makes people aggressive and addicted to it. Thus players should them-selves know about their limits. A study why people continue to play online Games. In search of critical design factors to increase customer loyalty to online contents, the result reveled that people continue to play when the have optimal experience when they playing online games. It can be attained if a player has effective personal interaction or pleasure social interaction.

Breeds Aggressive Behavior

In the most of the cases. It occurs that when a player attacks in a game. It results in increased negative emotions like anger and frustration. Thus make the players unable to control the emotions. It eventually increase the frustration more when they attack on the last minute as they come across many steps all that process. Which went in vain thus in furious.

Many players say that they became furious and shout at people when they are attacked at the last minute. It doesn't influence greatly when they attacked at starting of the match.

Experts from the interview are given below.

“It makes me little nervous increases the heart beat and killed in last minute makes me a tensed and through whatever I have”

“When I ever attacked in the last minute if the game. I used to

Move away from the for some period of time”

It's been widely said that attacked in the last minute of the game affects one's emotion very badly as it makes players aggressive than they were and it makes them feel so frustrated that they act far different from as they were. A research on when does frustration, not reduce continuance intention of online game? The results indicate that the frustration is negatively related to expectancy disconfirmation only for games with high gaming intensity, but not for gamers with long history (Lio,G, Huang, H., & Teng, C.,2016).

Physiological Disturbances

Playing online games gives pleasure as well it also produces some physiological disturbances in association with other factors. As players focused on playing Battle Ground Mobile India for a long period of time so that they hardly notice their health factors. They hardly mind that they are exposing themselves to brighter lights and stressing their eye muscles as well as their body. If it happens in the long run it might lead to some bodily ailments/dysfunctions.

Some players say that they experience irritability in their eyes when they play Battle Ground Mobile India for a long period of time, and they also experienced headache at times. They should be aware about controlling their play time in order to control the problems.

Excerpt from the interview are give

“As we are playing for hours it occasionally brings headaches and eye problems”

“Playing it for long hours with a high brightness level on the screen leads to irritation in the eye”

It is always true that using mobile phones for a long period of time with high brightness in the screen will increase eye problems. A study on effect of playing a computer game using bright display on pre-sleep physiological variables-sleep latency, slow wave sleep and REM sleep. The results indicate that playing an exciting computer game affects sleep latency and REM sleep but that a bright display does not affect sleep variables (Higuchi, S., Motohashi, Y., Liu, Y., & Maeda, A., 2005).

Improved Peer Relationship & Conformity

Sometimes the players of online games might increase because they wish to be a part of some group; moreover everyone avoids being unknown in the group. Also, People tend to experience what they get as feedback from their closed ones, thus, the feedback that is passed on from one individual to another.

Many players say that they came to know about Battle Ground Mobile India through their friend's ad also the reason behind continuing it also will be their friends. There is possibility playing Battle Ground Mobile India with friends, which motivates people to continue it and it provides more fun than any other game which played as a single player.

Excerpts from the interview are given:

“I know about Battle Ground Mobile India through my friends and they always motivates me to continue it.”

“I play Battle Ground Mobile India when my friends ask me to join with them, I rarely use it to play it when I'm alone”

Many times, people tend to avoid staying away from the peer environment so that they tend to irritate whatever is done by the close group members. Sometimes in order to mingle with new group members the topic that is trending might be used as an ice breaker. A study of Social interactions in massively multiplayer online role-playing gamers, results indicates that players tend to express themselves when they may not feel comfortable in expressing in the real life (Cole, H, & Griffiths, M,D., 2007)

Social Reciprocity

Social reciprocity is “how behavior of one person influences and is influenced by behavior of another person and vice versa”. This happens when a player attacks another player where some players intentionally wait for the opportunity while some others just take it as simple. Many respondents say they wish to attack the players who attacked him, given an opportunity. Some takes it so simple. Excerpts from the interview are given:

“When someone kills me, I tend to analyse how they affect me and tried to learn from my mistakes”

“When a players attacks me, it makes me so furious and shouts at them, wish to kill that person when I have the chance”

“It makes me a little nervous, increase heart beat; killed in the last minute makes me so tensed and threw whatever I have!”

It clearly evident that most of the players react over what was happening to them by compromising their real own self. They automatically tend to act depending on what happened in the Past: most of the players seem to look for the chance to give back what they experienced. A respondent pointed out that attacking the person who attacked is a difficult task, but if it happens it provides extreme level of pleasure

Denial/Avoidance of social life

Playing online games like Battle Ground Mobile India will gradually increase the playing time, thereby reducing the time with one. It gradually increases its importance over the people. So playing online games will make the person less aware about what surrounds them and the time they spend with their friends, family and significant others.

Some respondents note that they moved to a state where they need no companionship in a short period of time after playing Battle Ground Mobile India. Also, many players tend to ignore phone calls whenever they play Battle Ground Mobile India as attending phone calls during the match affect the match: mean time other player might attack them. So, they tend to ignore calls even it is important.

Experts from the interview are given:

“I used to ignore calls even if it is important during the match”

“it reduced the time that I spend with my friends and going out”

“Sometimes I play Battle Ground Mobile India as a time pass while sometimes I may not even notice what happens around me”

“I used to block my friends number as they intentionally call me to affect the match it sometimes leads to losing the chicken dinner”

Concentrating more on virtual world will eventually affect the relationship in the real world. Even though it connects those people who play the game, it certainly affects the social life with those who are not playing it. And also the individuals' connect with the community around. A study on the effects on escape from self and interpersonal relationship with the pathological use of internet. Denote that people tend to use online games more in order to distract themselves from the reality and the self (Kwon, J., Chung, C & Lee, J. 2011).

Improved Social Skills and Relationship

It's been said that playing online games will vigorously affect one's social life. This is not happening always. When the play is in control of the players it might be useful for them. When the limit is crossed the person might have to face negative consequences some respondent shared that they could connect/ network with old friends with whom they cannot have a regular conversation.

Experts from the interview are given:

“...we used to play Battle Ground Mobile India as it can help connect with their friends”

“it also reduces the impact of negative situations when we play it”

“Helps in forming new friends and maintaining relationship”

The game is designed in a way that any player from the world can join with any other player. Thus it seems to increase one's motivation to continue the game. The connectivity it provides serves as an important one and it's also been said that playing it can create and maintain relationship with others. A respondent says that playing Battle Ground Mobile India gave lot of friends as they started playing squad match. A study on exploring game experiences and game leader in massively multiplayer online role-playing games, indicated that game community and playing games in team increases one's leadership skills. There is also a significant positive relationship between in-game leadership and offline leadership (Jang, Y., & Ryu, S., 2011)

Decreased Awareness about the External World

As mentioned above, playing PUBG restricts the information that a person gathers from the external world. Also, the person might think about playing it most of the time, thus leading to a state where they don't know what know

what happens around them they highly concentrate on playing it. Sometimes it may happen at a minimal level that some players experienced flow when they play Battle Ground Mobile India.

Some respondents state that they might not be aware about what happens around them while playing it, and the time flies when they start playing it.

Experts from the interview given:

“While playing Battle Ground Mobile India I do not realize that my name was called out and only after few times I always realize”

“Even though on individual is in the group he seems to be individualizes”

It is true that an individual will be unable to notice what is happening around when they are fully involved to fully concentrate on the play alone, thus it makes them separate the real world. A study on the effect of personality on Online Game Flow experience and the eye blink rate as an objective indicator showed that the gamers who tend to be dominant or noncompliant were more likely to experience flow while the eye blink rate and perceptions of the external environment could be objective indicators of flow experience.

Compromises with Academic & Routine Task

Sometimes people tend to compromise with all other works in order to play PUBG, as the game provides more fun and entertainment than any other work. It's also a kind of motivating factors where it makes people to pursue it when they succeed in a match. Many respondents said that they compromised with many tasks like attending classes, completing signs and even routines like caning and sleeping.

Excerpts from the interview are given:

“Compromised with academic activities like writing assignments, preparing for exam and bunking classes”

"Compromises with regular duties like changes in bathing, sleeping and eating patterns.”

"Used to ignore calls when I play Battle Ground Mobile India”

"I used to compromise with food in college as I won't play Battle Ground Mobile India at home"

Playing a game always makes one feel good, so we focus mostly on playing games to obtain pleasure /happiness. One should know his/ her own limits and should set restrictions in order to protect themselves from the negative consequences. A paper on the educational benefits of video games to presents contradictory findings that s in it helps in improving player's self me esteem, reduction in reaction time and improved eye-hand coordination. In addition, video games also help in improving language skills, basic math skills, reading and social skills.

Summary and Conclusion

The number of players who play Battle Ground Mobile India increasing drastically from day to day; it's said that many were compromising on several other works. This research, particularly focused on exploring the reason behind continuing to play, and on changes that occurs in individuals - due to continual engagement with Battle Ground Mobile India. The changes that occur are sometimes within the individual, sometimes between the individuals and sometimes amongst the individuals. While it's reported that action video game players exhibit better visual attention, motor control abilities, focus, multitasking, and shrewd judgement, it was also found that these come with a cost loss of grey matter in hippocampus, which may, in a long run increase the risk of developing neuropsychiatric illness like PTSD, Depression, Alzheimer's, or Schizophrenia (G.L. Wet et.al, 2017). Some of the negative consequences within and between individuals because of being with Battle Ground Mobile India include gaming addiction, aggressive behavior, emotional distancing from the world around, cyberbullying, defaulting personal and professional commitments etc.

Battle Ground Mobile India players reports that this game helps in connecting with friends (who we otherwise would not speak or have spent much time with), improving their relationships with coplayers, and also helps in forming new relationships with others. Sometimes it seems to affect's one's relationship where the game connects those who play the Battle Ground Mobile India while the players have the difficulty in maintaining healthy relationships with non-players. Players were also found to avoid their friends and family when they play the game even though ignore the phone calls during the match even it seems to be important/urgent. In addition, while playing the Battle Ground Mobile India many players stay unaware about what happens around them, sometimes to an extent that they no more need of anyone's companionship when they were bored and alone.

References

- Billieux et.al., (2015) problematic involvement in online games a cluster analytic approach computers in human behaviour 43. 242b -250
- Chen. I.,S., Tu., H.H & wang. E.S.(2008) personality traits and life satisfaction among online game players. *Cyberpsychology & behaviour* .11(2), 145-149.
- Chen , S.W.,Yang ,C.H., Huang. K,S., & Fu. S.L., (2019) Digital games for learning energy conservation: a study of impacts on motivation. *Attention and learning outcomes innovation in education and teaching international* 56(1). 66-76.
- Chiang .Y.(2011) exploring online games player's flow experiences and positive affect the Turkish online journal of education technology. 10(1). 106-114.
- Choi, D.,& Kim, K. (2004) why people play online games: in search of critical design factors to increase customer loyalty to online contents *cyberpsychology and behaviour*. 7(1). 11-24
- Cole. H.,& Griffiths, M.D. (2007) social interaction in massively multiplayer online role playing gamer *cyberpsychology and behaviour*10(4).575-583. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2007.9988>.
- Ferguson. C.J. (2007). The good. The bad and the ugly: a meta analytic review of positive and negative affect of violent video games *psychiatric quarterly*. 78(4) 309-316
- Griffiths, M. 2002 the educational benefits of video games. *Education and health* 20(3). 47-51
- Gruser. S.M., Thalamann. P.D.R., Ph, D.C., Griffiths, M.D & Ph.d.(2007) excessive computer game playing: evidence of addiction and aggression/?.*cyberpsychology and behaviour* 10(2) 290-292 <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb2006.9956>
- Higiuch. S, motohashi. Y. Liu., Y., & Maeda, A. (2005) effects of playing a computer game using bright display on
- Hull, D.C., Williams, G.A., & Griffiths, M.D. (2013). Video game characteristics, happiness and flow as a predictors of addiction among video game players: A pilot study *Journal of Behavioural addictions*, 23), 145-152.
- Jang, Y., & Rye, S. (2011). Exploring game experiences and game leadership in massively multiplayer online rule playing games *Brinsh journal of educational technology*, 42(4), 616-623.
- Jeng, S., & Teng. C. (2008) Personality and motivations for playing online games *Social behaviour and Personality, an international journal*, 36(8), 1053-1060.
- Ko, C., D.M., Yen, J., D.M., Liu, S., & Huang, C. (2009). The Associations Between Aggressive Behaviors and Internet Addiction and Online Activities in Adolescents. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 44(6), 598-605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2008.11.011>.

- Ko, C., Yen, J., Chen, S., & Yen, C. (2005) Gender Differences and Related Factors Affecting Online. The journal of nervous and mental disease, 193(4), 273-277. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.nmd.0000158373.85150.57>.
- Kowert, R., Domahidi, E. & Quandt, T. (2014). The relationship between online video game involvement and game-related friendships among emotionally sensitive individuals. *Cyberpsychology, behaviour and social networking*, 17(1), 447-453.
- Kuss, D. J., Louws, J., & Wiers, R. W. (2012) Online Gaming Addiction? Motives predict addictive play behaviour in Massively Multiplayer Online Role- Playing Games *Cyberpsychology, behaviour and social networking*. 1-6.
- Kwon, J., Chung, C., & Lee, J. (2011). The effects of escape from self and interpersonal relationship on the pathological use of internet games. *Community mental health journal*, 47(1).20-121.
- Liao, G, Huang, H., & Teng, C. (2016). When does frustration not reduce prespective *Journal of electronic continuance intention of online games? The expectancy disconfirmation prespective journal of electronic commrcy research*. 17(1). 65.
- Liberman, D.A. (1997) Interactive vole games for health promotion Effects and health *Health promotion and interative technology Theoretical applications and future directions*, F10-120.
- Liebert, M. A., & Yee, N. (2006) Motivations for Play in Online Games *Cyber psychology and behavin* 916-772.775.
- Liu, M., & Peng, W. (2009) Cognitive and psychological predictors of the negative outcomes associated with playing MMOGS (massively multiplayer online games) *Computers in Human behaviour* 25(6), 1306-1311.
- Lee, M. (2009). Understanding the behavioural intention to play online games: an extension theory of planned behaviour *online information review* 33(5), 849-872.
- Mathews, C. L., Morrell, H. ER, & Molle, J.E. (2018). Video game addiction. ADHD symptomatology and video game reinforcement. *The American journal of drug and alcohol abuse*, 1-10.
- Mehroof, M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2010). Online Gaming Addiction/ The Role of Sensation senza seeking. Self-control Neuroticism, Aggression, State Anxiety and Trait Anxiety. *Cyberpsychology, behaviour and social networking*, 13(3). 313-316.
- Ng, B.D., Wiemer-hastings, P. & Ph. D. (2005). Addiction to the Internet and Online Gaming *Cyberpsychology and behaviour*, 8(2), 110-113.
- Rau, P. P., Tseng, Y. C., Dong, X., Jiang, C., & Chen, C. (2017). The effects of personality on online game flow experience and the eye blink rate as an objective indicator *Advances in human computer interaction*.28. Singh, M., (2018) Compulsive Digital gaming: An Emerging Mental Health Disorder in Children. *The Indian journal of Pediatrics*, 1-3.
- Trepte, S.,Reinecke, L.,& Juechems, K.The social side of gaming: How play online computer games creates online and offline social support. *Computer in human behaviour*, 28, 832-839. <https://doi.org/10.1026/j.chb.2011.12.003>
- Wei, H. T., Chen, M. H., Huang, P. C.,& Bai, Y.M. (2012). The Association between online gaming. Social phobia and depression: an internet survey. *BMC Psychiatry*. 12-92. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-12-92>
- Wu.J.(a.d.). The effects of trust and enjoyment on intention to play online games. *The journal of electronic commerce research*. 8(2) 128-140